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Predgovor

Međunarodna naučno stručna konferencija ETIKUM 2023 se održava tradicionalno već četrnaesti put. U vreme kada je koncipirana, 2006. godine, konferencija je osmišljena kao informativno-edukativna i naučno-stručna. Informativno-edukativna dimenzija se oslikava kroz učešće predavača iz redova stručnih predstavnika eminentnih proizvođača opreme koja se koristi u edukativnim i istraživačkim procesima na našem Fakultetu. Pri tome je akcenat na diseminaciji informacija i edukaciji u vezi sa tehnološkim novitetima u oblasti hardverskih i softverskih komponenti. Naučno-stručna dimenzija konferencije se ostvaruje kroz predstavljanje naučnih i stručnih rezultata, pre svega, iz oblasti koje obuhvata Katedra za metrologiju, kvalitet, pribore, alate i ekološko inženjerske aspekte. Pored toga, zahvaljujući razvoju interdisciplinarnе saradnje, konferencija je i ove godine obuhvatila i srodne naučno stručne oblasti, u okviru kojih članovi Katedre realizuju naučno-istraživačke i stručne projekte.

Od 2016. godine, uvedena je nagrada za najbolji rad mladog istraživača u znak sećanja na Prof. dr Janka Hodoliča. Programski odbor ETIKUM konferencije je i 2023. godine nagradio najbolji rad mladog istraživača ETIKUM konferencije sa Prof. dr Janko Hodolič nagradom.

Konferencija ETIKUM 2021 je strukturirana u tri tematske celine:

1. Metrologija i kontrola kvaliteta u proizvodnom inženjerstvu;
2. Metrologija i kontrola kvaliteta u biomedicinskom inženjerstvu;
3. Metrologija i kvalitet u zaštiti životne sredine i zaštiti na radu;

Prva tematska oblast je, pored klasičnih aspekata metrologije i kvaliteta u oblasti proizvodnog mašinstva, obuhvatila i precizno inženjerstvo, odnosno nano metrologiju i srodne tehnologije.

U okviru druge tematske oblasti su predstavljeni rezultati aktivnosti u oblasti biomedicinskog inženjerstva od strane istraživača i sa drugih departmana FTN-a.

Treća tematska oblast privukla je istraživače iz različitih oblasti zaštite životne i radne sredine. U okviru treće tematske oblasti predstavljena su istraživanja vezana za merenja i analize zagađujućih materija emitovanih u vazduh, vodu, zemljište, merenje i monitoring fizičkih aspekata životne sredine kao što su buka, zračenje i vibracije, kao i ocenjivanje životnog ciklusa proizvoda i procesa.

Na konferenciji ETIKUM 2023 je prezentovano ukupno 64 naučnih i stručnih radova, dok je u radu konferencije učestvovalo preko 80 predavača i slušalaca iz akademskih institucija i privrede iz više evropskih zemalja. Prethodno pomenute činjenice predstavljaju, sa jedne strane, potvrdu koncepcije konferencije, a sa druge strane, garanciju da će konferencija ETIKUM i narednih godina predstavljati značajan informativno-edukativni i naučno-stručni događaj na ovim geografskim prostorima.

Foreword

International Scientific-Expert Conference ETIKUM 2023 will be held for the fourteenth time and it has become a tradition. When established in 2006, the conference is designed as informative-educational and scientific-expert. Informative and educational dimension is reflected through the participation of lecturers from among expert representatives of the eminent manufacturers of equipment connected to educational and research processes at the Faculty. Moreover, the emphasis are on the dissemination of information as well as on education in relation to technological innovations related to both - hardware and software components. Scientific and expert, i.e., professional dimensions of conference are achieved through the presentation of scientific and expert results, primarily from the field of the Chair of metrology, quality, fixtures, tools and ecological-engineering aspects. In addition, thanks to the development of interdisciplinary cooperation, the conference this year included the related scientific and technical fields, in which Chair members implement research and professional projects.

From 2016, in memoriam of Prof. dr Janko Hodolic, an award for the best paper of the young researcher was introduced. The best paper of the young researcher from ETIKUM 2023 conference was rewarded with the "Prof dr Janko Hodolic" award on behalf of the ETIKUM conference Programme committee.

In the context of this conception, the conference was divided into three thematic sections:

- 1. Metrology and quality control in the production engineering;*
- 2. Metrology and quality control in the biomedical engineering;*
- 3. Metrology and quality in the field of environmental protection and occupational safety.*

The first thematic area, in addition to the classical aspects of metrology and quality in the field of production engineering, included subjects related to precision engineering and nano metrology and related technologies.

The second thematic area presented the results of activities in the field of biomedical engineering conducted by researchers from various departments of the Faculty of Technical Sciences (FTN).

The third thematic area this year attracted researchers from various areas of environmental protection and occupational safety. Research in field of measurement and analysis of pollutants to air, water, and soil, measurement and monitoring of physical aspects of environment such as noise, radiation and vibrations, as well as life cycle assessment of products and processes is presented in third thematic area.

At ETIKUM 2023 conference 64 scientific-expert papers were presented, while the conference was attended by over 80 speakers and listeners from academia and business from several European countries. The previously mentioned facts are, on the one hand, the confirmation of the conference's concept, and on the other hand, a guarantee that the ETIKUM conference will be considered as important informative and educational, scientific and professional event in these regions.

Novi Sad, December 2023

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Vučinić, P., Petrović, Đ., Ivić, S., Puškar, T., Radumilo, D., Puškar, N., Vućinić T.

CONTEMPORARY ADVANCES IN AUTOMATED LANDMARK DETECTION IN CEPHALOMETRICS

Abstract: Contemporary methods for automatic landmark detection in cephalometrics are based on the results and positive experiences of traditional techniques such as edge detection or AAM and utilize cutting-edge technologies, including deep learning and machine learning algorithms. These advanced approaches harness convolutional neural networks and other sophisticated models to achieve robust and accurate identification of anatomical landmarks on cephalometric images. These methods transcend traditional limitations, accommodating variations in anatomy and enhancing precision. The synergy of these contemporary methods not only revolutionizes orthodontic practices but also contributes to interdisciplinary research, propelling the field towards a future of enhanced diagnostics and treatment planning.

Key Words: Artificial intelligence; Cephalometric landmarks; Computer vision; Deep Learning

1. INTRODUCTION

Cephalometrics, the study of the head's skeletal and soft tissue structures, plays a pivotal role in orthodontics, anthropology, and forensic science. Traditionally, cephalometric analysis involved manual identification of landmarks on X-ray images, a time-consuming and error-prone process. However, with the advent of advanced computational techniques, automated landmark detection has revolutionized this field [1,2]. This introduction provides an overview of the contemporary knowledge in automated landmark detection in cephalometrics, exploring the techniques, challenges, and applications that have emerged in recent years.

2. HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

The journey of automated landmark detection in cephalometrics traces back to the early applications of computer vision and pattern recognition in the mid-20th century. Early attempts focused on basic geometric features, paving the way for more sophisticated algorithms in subsequent decades. Progress accelerated with the availability of high-resolution imaging technologies and computational power.

Early attempts (1950s - 1970s): The roots of automated landmark detection in cephalometrics can be traced back to the 1950s when computer technology began to emerge. Early attempts focused on basic geometric features and edge detection algorithms. Researchers explored

methods to identify specific points on X-ray images manually, which laid the foundation for subsequent automated approaches [3,4].

Introduction of computer vision (1980s - 1990s): The 1980s and 1990s witnessed significant progress in computer vision techniques. Researchers started applying image processing algorithms to identify edges and shapes within cephalometric images. Template matching methods were also explored, where predefined templates of landmarks were compared with the image data to detect specific points [5,6].

Integration of machine learning (1990s - 2000s): As machine learning gained traction, researchers began integrating these techniques into cephalometric landmark detection. Supervised learning algorithms, such as neural networks and support vector machines, were employed to train models on labeled datasets. These models could identify landmarks based on learned patterns from the training data, marking a shift from rule-based systems to data-driven approaches [7,8].

Advancements in 3D imaging (2000s - 2010s): With the advent of 3D imaging technologies, such as cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT), the scope of cephalometric analysis expanded. Automated landmark detection algorithms evolved to handle 3D data, allowing for more comprehensive analyses of craniofacial structures. These advancements paved the way for a more detailed understanding of anatomical landmarks in three-dimensional space.

Rise of deep learning (2010s - present): The 2010s marked a significant turning point with the rise of deep learning techniques, especially convolutional neural networks (CNNs). CNNs excel at learning hierarchical features from images, making them highly effective for landmark detection tasks. Deep learning models were trained on large datasets, enabling them to automatically extract complex features and accurately identify landmarks in cephalometric images [9].

Integration of augmented reality (present and future): In recent years, the integration of automated landmark detection with augmented reality (AR) technologies has gained attention. AR applications overlay virtual information onto the real world, allowing clinicians to visualize cephalometric landmarks in real-time during patient examinations. This integration enhances the precision of landmark identification and facilitates better communication between clinicians and patients.

2.1 Traditional image processing techniques:

- Edge detection algorithms
- Template matching methods

Active Appearance Models (AAMs) are statistical models used in computer vision and image analysis to capture shape and texture variations in images. In the context of automated detection of landmarks in cephalometrics, AAMs are employed to model the appearance and shape of craniofacial structures, allowing for accurate and robust landmark detection. AAM approach involves the following series of procedures:

1. Data acquisition and preprocessing: High-quality cephalometric images of patients are collected using X-ray imaging techniques, ensuring consistent positioning and image resolution. Cephalometric images then undergo preprocessing steps, including noise reduction, contrast enhancement, and normalization, to standardize the image quality and make them suitable for analysis.

2. Shape and texture modeling: A set of manually annotated landmarks is used to create a shape model, representing the spatial arrangement of landmarks. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is commonly employed to reduce the dimensionality of shape variations, capturing the main modes of shape variation in the data. The texture of the cephalometric image is modeled using pixel intensities within a local region around each landmark. PCA is again applied to reduce the dimensionality of texture variations, capturing the main modes of texture variation in the data.

3. Building the Active Appearance Model: The shape and texture models are combined to create the Active Appearance model. This model represents the relationship between the shape and texture variations observed in the training dataset. The combined model encapsulates the statistical information necessary to generate new instances of cephalometric images with plausible landmark locations.

4. Landmark localization: During the landmark detection process, an initial estimate of landmark locations is obtained either manually or using a simpler algorithm. This initialization serves as a starting point for the AAM-based optimization. The AAM then optimizes the landmark positions iteratively, aligning the shape and texture models with the input image. The optimization process seeks the best-fitting instance of the AAM in the image space, refining the landmark positions to match the actual landmarks in the cephalometric image. AAMs can be constrained to ensure plausible deformations, preventing unrealistic shapes and textures. Constraints are often derived from anatomical knowledge and incorporated into the optimization process.

5. Evaluation and refinement: The accuracy of landmark detection is evaluated by comparing the automatically detected landmarks with manually annotated ground truth landmarks. Metrics such as Euclidean distance or mean squared error are commonly used to measure the accuracy of landmark localization. Based on the evaluation results, the AAM can be refined by incorporating additional training data, refining the shape and texture models, or adjusting the initialization and optimization strategies to improve landmark detection accuracy.

In our research, which we conducted and published in 2010, an average accuracy in cephalometric landmark detection of 1.68 mm was obtained, with 61 per cent of landmarks detected within 2 mm and 95 per cent of landmarks detected within 5 mm precision. A noticeable increase in overall precision and detection of low-contrast cephalometric landmarks was achieved compared with other automated systems of that time [10].

2.2 Machine learning approaches:

- Supervised learning algorithms (e.g., neural networks, support vector machines).
- Unsupervised learning techniques (e.g., clustering algorithms) [11,12].

2.3 Deep learning architectures:

- Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and their variants.
- Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) for sequential data analysis [13,14].

Fig. 1. Artificial intelligence approaches to identify landmarks

3. CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS

Despite significant advancements, automated landmark detection faces several challenges, including image noise, anatomical variations, and occlusions. Additionally, ensuring robustness, accuracy, and real-time processing remains a persistent challenge.

Image quality and noise: Cephalometric images can vary in quality due to factors like exposure settings, patient positioning, and equipment differences. Noise, artifacts, and distortions in the images can hinder accurate landmark detection. Preprocessing techniques, such as noise reduction and contrast enhancement, are applied to improve image quality.

Anatomical variations: Human anatomy exhibits natural variations, and landmarks may appear differently and can deviate significantly from the standard positions in different individuals. Training machine learning models on diverse datasets encompassing various demographics and conditions can improve the system's ability to handle anatomical variations.

Occlusions and overlapping structures: Landmarks may be obscured by other anatomical structures, dental appliances, or radiopaque materials, leading to partial or complete occlusions. Detecting obscured landmarks accurately is a

complex task. Techniques like semantic segmentation can help identify regions of interest, aiding in landmark localization even when they are partially visible.

Landmark ambiguity: Some anatomical features might lack distinct boundaries, making it difficult to pinpoint exact landmark locations. Expert knowledge and anatomical constraints can guide landmark detection algorithms. Integrating domain-specific rules and constraints into the algorithms can help resolve ambiguity to some extent.

Computational complexity and processing time: Deep learning models, especially complex architectures like deep neural networks, demand significant computational resources. Researchers are continually working on optimizing algorithms and developing hardware accelerators tailored for deep learning tasks (parallel processing, distributed computing, etc.)

Algorithmic bias: Automated landmark detection algorithms can be biased based on the training data, leading to inaccurate results, especially for underrepresented demographic groups. Addressing algorithmic bias requires diverse and representative training datasets. Techniques like adversarial training and fairness-aware machine learning are employed to reduce bias [15].

4. CONCLUSION

Automated landmark detection in cephalometrics represents a transformative paradigm shift, enhancing the accuracy, efficiency, and reliability of craniofacial analyses. The AI is a promising tool for facilitating cephalometric tracing in routine clinical practice as well as analyzing large databases for research purposes. Despite the advancements, challenges such as anatomical variations, occlusions, and ethical concerns persist. Ongoing research focuses on addressing these challenges through diverse and representative datasets, advanced algorithms, and ethical frameworks.

Additionally, the future of automated landmark detection in cephalometrics is likely to see further integration with artificial intelligence, leading to more intelligent and adaptive systems. The main objective of this narrative review was to assist clinicians and researchers in comprehending various features of this study area.

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